

Investigating Roughness and Hardness Perception Through Vibrotactile Augmentation of Tangible Textures

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Abstract. We investigate whether a small set of tangible 3D-printed textures can be augmented with vibrotactile feedback to render a broader set of texture sensations. Our approach combines hair-like printed textures, which modulate perceived hardness, with transverse sinusoidal vibrations, which modulate perceived roughness. We ran two user studies: a haptic-only study and a visuo-haptic study in VR. This paper presents preliminary results showing that vibrotactile augmentation can modulate the perceived roughness of physical textures in haptic-only interaction, and investigates how these effects extend to visuo-haptic interaction in VR, where visuo-haptic matching was impacted by hardness but not roughness.

1 Introduction

Haptic feedback is important for immersion in virtual environments, but realistic texture rendering remains difficult to scale: passive haptics often require many props, whereas fully active devices can reduce naturalness or constrain interaction [2]. Our approach combines passive and active tactile cues by augmenting 3D-printed hair-like textures with vibrotactile stimulation. More specifically, we use hair-like structures to provide variations in perceived hardness [4], and augment them with transverse sinusoidal vibrations, which can alter roughness perception [1,3].

This paper explores how vibrotactile augmentation of 3D-printed hair-like textures is perceived in haptic-only and visuo-haptic conditions, and reports findings from both evaluations.

2 Experimental Setup

We replicated five hair-like textures suggested by previous work [4] with structure lengths ranging from 0 to 10 mm. Consistent with prior work, increasing hair length had a strong effect on perceived hardness and only a limited effect on

perceived roughness [4]. We then integrated these textures into a PLA tangible device containing a Dayton Audio DAEX19CT actuator (Figure 1). Vibrations were triggered only when finger motion was detected by an overhead camera tracking the finger at 60 fps.

Fig. 1. Vibrotactile device used to augment the tangible textures. (A) CAD design illustrating the overall device structure, (B) Assembled device showing the texture mounted on top plate and, (C) Internal view revealing the actuation module, where the actuator is embedded in silicone.

3 User Studies

Haptic-only study. Twenty participants explored two hair-like textures (2.5 and 10 mm) augmented with 16 sinusoidal vibration signals obtained by crossing four frequencies (100, 125, 150, and 175 Hz) and four displacement amplitudes (3, 5, 8, and 11 μm), and rated the perceived roughness (Figure 2 (A)). Vibration amplitude significantly affected perceived roughness, especially on the 2.5 mm texture ($p = 0.008$). Hierarchical clustering revealed three perceptually distinct roughness levels for each texture, supported by an ANOVA performed on the most distant vibrotactile signals across clusters ($p < 0.05$). Representative signals were 100 Hz–3 μm , 100 Hz–11 μm , and 150 Hz–11 μm for the 2.5 mm texture, and 100 Hz–3 μm , 125 Hz–5 μm , and 125 Hz–11 μm for the 10 mm texture.

Visuo-haptic VR study. Twelve participants then completed a 3AFC matching task in VR using the same two physical textures, each tested without vibration and with two vibration-induced roughness levels. Five virtual objects were selected to cover different roughness–hardness sensations. Matching ratings were analyzed with a cumulative link mixed model for ordinal responses, followed by planned post-hoc contrasts on estimated marginal means with Holm correction. Roughness modulation did not significantly affect matching ratings relative to the baseline. Instead, ratings were mainly driven by hardness, induced by the textures hair length: the difference between the 2.5 and 10mm textures was significant overall ($p < 0.001$) and remained visible for several objects (Figure 2 (B) and (C)).

Fig. 2. Experimental setups and representative results. (A) Haptic-only study setup, (B) Visuo-haptic study setup, (C) Visuo-haptic study results, showing selection probabilities (top) and matching ratings (bottom).

4 Discussion and Future Work

These results suggest that, while vibrotactile augmentation can structure different roughness levels in tactile-only interaction, these variations were not strong enough to affect visuo-haptic texture perception. This indicates that future work should strengthen roughness modulation so that it becomes more noticeable relative to the texture’s underlying mechanical properties. In addition, the 3D-printed hair-like structures used here may not be the best base for matching a broader range of virtual objects. Future work should also explore other physical texture structures that may provide a better basis.

Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange. Several questions remain open. First, how can roughness modulation be made more noticeable relative to the baseline hardness of the underlying tangible texture? Second, are there alternative structures, materials, or augmentation mechanisms that could better support clear, balanced modulations of both roughness and hardness while remaining simple to implement? More broadly, our results raise the question of how roughness and hardness cues are weighted in visuo-haptic exploration, and why hardness dominated matching judgments in the present setup. Addressing these questions would benefit from interdisciplinary discussions with researchers in mechatronics, neuroscience, and materials science.

References

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